

Efficient Biometric Template based Authentication Scheme for Grid Environment

G. Jasper Willisie Kathrine[#], E. Kirubakaran^{*}, Elijah Blessing Rajsingh[§]

[#] Department of Information Technology, Karunya University, Tamil Nadu, India
meet.katee@gmail.com

^{*} BHEL, Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India
ekiru@bheltry.co.in

[§] School of Computer Science and Technology, Karunya University, Tamil Nadu, India
elijahblessings@karunya.edu

Abstract

Decentralization in every walk of life has resulted in the development of Distributed Computing. Distributed Networks have led to the wide spread use of Grid computing for educational, research and data sharing. Data sharing and data access depends on their availability, capability, cost and user requirements. One of the major needs for a secure Grid Environment is a strong authentication for users in the Grid Environment. Since Authentication is the entry point into every network, a novel smart card based authentication scheme has been proposed. The proposed authentication scheme recommends the use of the biometric template of the finger of the user embedded in a smart card along with the ID and password of the user. The Time efficient performance of the proposed scheme in comparison with the existing Secure Socket Layer based authentication scheme is discussed. The attacks which the proposed scheme is able to withstand are also discussed. Performance analysis also proves that the proposed scheme completes user authentication in a secure less time.

Key word: Distributed Computing, Biometric, Grid Computing, Authentication

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1. Introduction

Grid computing involves sharing heterogeneous resources which are located in geographically distributed places belonging to different administrative domains [1]. Grid data sharing is not file exchange but rather access to computers, software, data and other resources. Grid involves the creation of a dynamic Virtual Organization (VO). Each virtual organization comprises of users and their resources and any other services (S) joined by a common goal [2]. Each of the user or resource is available from different administrative domains (DO). Each user/resource have their own trust policy which requires a local to global and global to local mapping of the access policies as discussed in [3].

The basic security for the Globus Toolkit (GT 4) is the Grid Security Infrastructure (GSI) [4-5]. It depends on the Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), X.509 Proxy certificates and Transport Layer Security (TLS) for authentication. GSI involves third party verification for authorization. The GT framework is based on the Open Grid Services Architecture (OGSA) which uses the Secure Socket Layer (SSL) based on TLS. The GSI security is secure enough but has scalability problems [5].

The existing authentication schemes are based on the user name and the password and certificates which are generated by a secure Certificate Authority (CA) [5]. The existing authentication schemes belong to two factor authentication scheme which involves user name/password and some cards like those used in Banks. The Security for the Grid Environment is deployed in the middleware

which is used to access the grid network. Examples of Grid middleware are UNICORE (Uniform Interface to Computing Resources) [6], Globus [6], Legion [7] and Gridbus [8].

In [9] a Four-Factor based Biometric Authentication has been proposed. But the addition of location does not guarantee the avoidance of insider attack. The proposed authentication scheme optimizes the security of a grid environment by adding more features like biometric data in a smart card for optimal authentication.

User authentication has been in discussion for a long time to enhance the security of any system at the entry level itself. Many methods such as password based systems, ID based systems, and etc have been used. A hash-chain based remote user authentication in which all the passwords are encoded is given in [10]. In all the initial remote based authentication systems, a verifier table is to be placed in the server side which becomes a problem if the server is compromised.

Based on the existing remote authentication systems, an enhanced system is designed. In order to avoid maintaining a verifier table Hwang et al., proposed a non-interactive smart card based scheme without verifier tables [11]. A finger print based remote user authentication scheme was proposed in [12]. This scheme was found to be vulnerable to masquerade attacks and many other attacks [13], [14]. In [15], [16], [17], the biometric data itself is taken as a key for encryption/decryption. The secret data is extracted by using the biometric template as the key. The biometric data is to be stored in the server side and used for comparison. But for effective Biometric authentication, the process is to be done in the client side [18] to avoid any problem due to the server being compromised [19]. In [20], the method has been optimized with the matching being done in the server side. But the server does not store any biometric data in its database thereby protecting the privacy of the user.

The method in [20] provides a three factor authentication which is password – something the user knows; smart card – something the user has; biometrics – something the user is. A further enhancement to this type of authentication is to add a fourth factor thereby providing a four factor authentication. The fourth factor can be the addition of location of the user – something the user is. The military data sharing requirements take into consideration the place in which the user is positioned so as to find the location of any valid/invalid user. So, the sensitive areas of application require security with some amount of privacy preservation. By combining the biometric data with passwords and the location of the user, the security factors are further enhanced.

2. Existing Security Framework For Grid

Alternate authentication schemes have been proposed such as a scalable Grid Information System (GIS) architecture in [21], and a Daonity two level based security architecture [22]. Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) based Authentication Schemes for Grid has been presented in [23]-[25]. Public Key Infrastructure and PMI (Privilege Management Infrastructure) combined scheme has been presented in [26].

Identity (ID) based grid authentication schemes have made use of ID tables and ID hierarchies along with an ID Revocation List (IRL) [27-28]. A combined security architecture based on Identity and PKI was presented in [29] which makes use of the password based TLS framework for implementing its authentication Scheme.

Figure 1. Biometric Template Generation

In all such schemes, the storage of the user credentials and maintenance of an ID table is required along with an Identity Revocation List (IRL). The key revocation in an ID based set up is complicated. Moreover ID based schemes suffer from key escrow problem which is related to key management.

As an alternate to the existing scheme and to increase the security, more user data is to be utilized for user authentication. Hence instead of deciding on an image based scheme which is also vulnerable to attacks it is proposed to use an image section of the user itself. Biometric involves various human features like facial features, gait, palm print, retina, iris, hand geometry, hand vein, etc. The most common easy and accurate feature that can be analyzed is the fingerprint. The fingerprint and its liveness can be deduced due to the increase in sensitivity level of sensors and the decrease and accuracy of such devices. The biometric template formation is as shown in figure 1. In many cases the image and its cross section of scanning can be done as in x-ray or blood verification but due to the intrusive nature of the scheme, it is avoided.

3. Proposed authentication system

Based on the details provided by the user along with the inputs given by the server, the smart card data is stored and given to the user through a secure medium. Only during the Login and the mutual authentication phase is the user and the server authenticated to each other. Once the mutual authentication is a success, then the user can go on to the next operation involved in the data transaction.

The server stores both the asymmetric and symmetric key in its database. Once a user requests for registration, the server accepts the user's hashed password in a secure way. This way assures that the server does not know the actual data and neither is data stored openly in any database within the server. The validity of the user is checked based on the comparison of the hashed data rather than the original data. This method of storage makes sure that the user's data is not lost under any circumstance. The proposed scheme is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. Proposed Authentication Methodology

The biometric data and a user ID and password are collected during each login and after it is verified by the smart card, the data is sent to the authentication server (AS). The AS then gathers the role of the user for that intra-domain from the Trusted Authority (TA) after verifying the user credentials.

All the hashed data are stored in the Registration/Authentication server's database and the encrypted data required for the further use of the user is stored in the smart card and sent to the user. The user then uses the smart card for further access to the Grid environment. The smart card does the initial validation of the user and then forwards the user data to the server, where further authentication is the done. In the proposed scheme, both the user and the server validate each other and hence it is complete mutual authentication. Only when the user and the server both satisfy the validation criteria then the data transfer occurs. If the user validation does not succeed it is rejected or the user is requested to start the authentication from the beginning of the login phase. The next section gives the detailed explanation of each phase of the proposed authentication system.

3.1 Details of the Authentication Scheme

This authentication scheme involves using a smart card which holds the data of what the user is i.e., the biometric data (B), what the user knows i.e., the password (PW) and the data that the user has i.e., smart card, Identifier (ID). This scheme has three phases such as Registration Phase, Login phase and a mutual authentication phase. The added features are the dynamic User ID (CID) and the dynamic server ID (SID). The Registration/Authentication server is configured to support symmetric and asymmetric encryption and decryption. In grid a client at one scenario can be the server at the next instant since it has to satisfy a need. Hence this system should be in such a way that each user is able to identify the requestor of the resource by his/her credentials. The flow of the process can be divided into a registration phase, a login phase and a mutual authentication phase. The notations used in this paper are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Notations used in this Paper

S	Server
U_i	User
S_{ID}	Identity of Server S_i
ID_i	Identity of User U_i
B_i	Biometric data of U_i
(PW_i)	Password of U_i
$h(.)$	One-way hash function
x	The master secret key
(P_k, S_k)	Public-private key pair
\oplus	The Exclusive-OR Operation
\parallel	Message Concatenation
R	Random Number generated by U_i
n_u	Nonce value generated by U_i
n_s	Nonce value generated by the server S_i

3.2 Registration Phase

During the registration phase, the user tries to register for a grid membership within a Virtual Organization (VO). During the membership registration, the user is given a particular Identifier (ID_i). The user registers his/her biometric data (B_i) which maybe a fingerprint or an iris template. The user also selects a random number r and a password (PW_i).

----- (1)The process flow of the proposed authentication scheme is shown in fig. 3.

Figure 3. Process of the Proposal Authentication Scheme

The following are the series of steps done in the server:

- a. Server generates public-private key pair (p_k, s_k) for asymmetric encryption/decryption.
- b. Server generates a secret key x for symmetric encryption/decryption.
- c. Both (x, s_k) are kept secure in the server.

The operations done at the user side are:

- a. The user records his/her user Identifier (ID_i)
- b. The user records the biometric template (B_i)
- c. The user selects a random string r and password (PW_i)

The user computes $SB_i = \delta(B_i) = h(r \oplus h(B_i))$. The value of SB_i is sent to the server securely along with the one-way hash function $h(.)$ of the Password and the identifier (ID_i) of the user. The server receives $(ID_i, h(PW_i), SB_i)$ through a secure channel. By using the values sent by the user, the server computes, y_i such that,

$$y_i = E_x (ID_i \parallel h(PW_i) \parallel SB_i) \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

where $E_x(.)$ represents the symmetric encryption using the secret key x . The server stores the user's password (PW_i) and the related identifier (ID_i) of the user and the calculated y_i .

The operations continued in the server side are:

- a. Server computes $K = h(ID_i \parallel x)$
- b. Server stores $(K, h(.), p_k)$ in the smart card.
- c. Server sends smart card to the user securely.

Once the user receives the smart card, a few entries are to be stored in it along with the data already available in the smart card i.e., y_i

The following operations are done to confirm the registration:

- a. The user enters the biometric data which can be an iris data /fingerprint B_i
- b. The user encrypts the random number r with PW_i such that $E_{PW_i}(r)$ is obtained.
- c. $E_{PW_i}(r)$ is stored in the smart card.
- d. $SB_i = \delta(B_i) = h(r \oplus h(B_i))$ is stored in the smart card.

3.3 Login Phase

A user U_i is allowed to enter the grid environment using his/her smart card. The user enters his/her Password (PW) and does a biometric scan denoted by E_i^* . The user's smart card retrieves the random value "r" from $E_{PW}(r)$ by using the password (PW) entered by the user U_i . The smart card computes $SB_i^* = \delta(SB_i) = h(r \oplus h(E_i^*))$. This value is compared with the already stored value of $SB_i = \delta(B_i) = h(r \oplus h(B_i))$ to confirm if the user is the same. Then the smart card generates a nonce value " n_u " and computes $M = (K \oplus n_u)$. Then CID_i is calculated such that, $CID_i = h(ID_i \parallel n_u)$

Then value of C_0 is computed such that,

$$C_0 = E_{p_k} (M \parallel CID_i \parallel y_i \parallel u) \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

Where $E_{p_k}(.)$ denotes the encryption function using the server's public key. "u" is the random value selected by the user during login time. To ensure the liveness of the user, a nonce value is added in the value of C_0 along with the already existing random values to add more security. C_0 is sent to the server.

3.4 Mutual Authentication Phase

Once C_0 is received by the server, the server does the following operations,

- Server decrypts C_0 using its private key s_k
- Server computes " n_s^* " such that $n_s^* = M \oplus K$ where $K = h(ID_i \parallel x)$. The server uses the ID_i obtained from y_i .
- The validity of the user is checked by using the Identifier ID_i to the one received by the server. By using the value of n_s^* the value of CID_i^* is calculated.
- Then the value of CID_i^* is compared with the value of CID_i to check if $CID_i = CID_i^*$.
- Also the value of ID_i can be verified with the ID stored in the ID table for the users at the server end. A comparison of ID's is done to make sure that verification is done correctly even when the Server ID table is corrupted.
- The remaining terms of C_0 i.e., $(h(PW_i) \parallel SB_i)$ is retained for future reference.

Server computes a values of C_1 such that

$$C_1 = E_u (N \parallel SED \parallel S_{ID} \parallel v) \text{-----} (3)$$

Where S_{ID} = Server's identity and v is the random number chosen by the server and u is the random number selected by the user and sent in C_0 . The server generates a nonce value " n_s " and computes $N = (K \oplus n_s)$. From the value of n_s , the value of the symmetric key u is generated. Server ID $SED = h(S_{ID} \parallel n_s)$. The dynamic ID and n_s is used to make sure that the data was not tampered during transmission. Server sends C_1 to the user U_i .

In the User Side, the following operations are done,

- The smart card decrypts C_1 using the random value of u .
- The value of S_{ID} is checked for valid server ID. The smart card computes $SED^* = h(S_{ID} \parallel n_s^*)$ using its nonce value n_s^* . Smart Card computes " n_s^* " such that $n_s^* = N \oplus K$ where $K = h(ID_i \parallel x)$.
- Then SED^* is calculated by using the value of the generated n_s^* and ID_i , i.e., $SED^* = h(S_{ID} \parallel n_s^*)$. If $SED^* = SED$, then the server is valid and the data has not been tampered with.

The smart card calculates the following value

$$C_2 = E_v (h(PW_i) \parallel SB_i) \text{-----} (4)$$

The server decrypts C_2 using v and calculates the value of y_i^* from the values sent in C_2 . If it is confirmed that $y_i^* = y_i$, then the server does a comparison of the values of the password and the biometric template to confirm the authenticity of the user.

If an attacker is to attack, he/she has to deduce the random and the nonce values which makes the attack much difficult. The value of SB_i^* in C_2 is compared with SB_i of y_i . If the value match is within a threshold range then the user is confirmed valid. The three phases are considered for computing the cost since they will be used repeatedly. Once all the steps have been completed successfully, it is clear that mutual authentication of both the user and the server is done for login of the user. The server secret number v can be used as a session key material and $h(v)$ can be used as a session key which is shared with the server.

3.5 Password Change Phase

The user U_i is authenticated by using the Password (PW) used initially for login process. Once authenticated, the user is prompted to enter the new password. Once the new password (PW'') is

entered, the $y_1 = E_x(\text{ID}_i \parallel h(\text{PW}_i) \parallel \text{SB}_i)$ value of $h(\text{PW}_i)$ is replaced with the value of $h(\text{PW}_i')$. An intimation of the password change is given to the server and it replaces the old password for the user identifier with the new password. Thereby the user is allowed to further login by using the new password.

4. Security Analysis of the proposed Authentication Scheme

In this section, the security and performance analysis of the proposed authentication scheme are presented. The attacks which are withstood by the proposed scheme of authentication are explained.

4.1 ID-Theft Attack

As in equation $C_0 = E_{pk}(M \parallel \text{CID}_i \parallel y_1 \parallel u)$, a dynamic user ID named as CID_i is created by the smart card based on the nonce value n_u instead of using the user's own ID. This helps to withstand the ID-theft attack and also preserves the privacy of the user.

4.2 Clock Synchronization and Replay Attack Problem

The problem in timestamp based authentication is replay attack due to the transmission delays in an unpredictable network. Even though the networks are fast the speed may vary based on the geographical and political distribution. To avoid using of timestamps, a nonce value n_u is used each time the user sends his/her data and a nonce value n_s is also used by the server to proclaim the server's validity. Since a nonce value such as n_u and n_s in equations $C_0 = E_{pk}(M \parallel \text{CID}_i \parallel y_1 \parallel u)$ where $M = (K \oplus n_u)$ and $C_1 = E_u(N \parallel \text{SED} \parallel S_{ID} \parallel v \parallel \text{pos}_s)$ where $N = (K \oplus n_s)$ can be used only once, and not repeated, the user/server can be safeguard themselves from replay attacks.

4.3 Modification Attack

Each authentication message in from equation (1), (2), (3) and (4) include a one-way hash function along with an encryption algorithm. The hash value in each equation requires a nonce value or a random value. Even if the attacker gets hold of each of these equations the decryption part and breaking the hash function is not possible. If the attacker has the value of $h(\text{PW}_i)$, to find the password, the attacker needs find an equivalent of the hash function by trying each password. This attack is difficult because the attacker has to first break into the encrypted data $C_0 = E_{pk}(M \parallel \text{CID}_i \parallel y_1 \parallel u)$. The attacker then needs to send the correct dynamic ID using the nonce. For an attacker to get all the values correct is impossible which makes modification attack difficult. Without knowing the actual data of these two values, the original data cannot be modified. Modification of the equations will be noted by the legitimate user and server and since all the messages are linked, it makes modification attack harder.

4.4 Mutual Authentication

At the end of the mutual authentication phase, both the server and the client authenticate each other thereby establishing mutual authentication. During each phase, of the equations C_0, C_1 and C_2 , the user and server check the validity of each other using the values of $\text{CID}, \text{SED}, M, N$. If the server has any doubt in the validity of the user, the message C_2 can be asked to be resent.

4.5 Man-in-the-middle Attack

An attacker who tries to do a man-in-the middle attack needs to know the decryption keys u, v and r in each message signal else its message will be discarded by the server or the client.

4.6 Security of the Stored Data on the Smart Card

The smart card holds the value of $(\text{ID}_i, y_i, h(\cdot), p_k)$ where, $y_i = E_x(\text{ID}_i \parallel h(\text{PW}_i) \parallel \text{SB}_i)$. If the smart card is compromised, the data it provides is not easily accessible to the attacker. Without

knowing the matching password and the ID of the user, the attacker cannot move further along the authentication phase. Knowing the public key of the server complicates matters since the attacker has to find the encryption algorithm and a matching value of C_0 to send to the server. Furthermore, the hash function has to be broken in order to get the secret data. The biometric data is stored in the open for anyone to copy it. It is stored in the form of a template combined with a random string which needs to be found to get the data. Thus the data stored in the smart card is secure.

5. Implementation of the proposed Authentication Scheme

In this section, the performance and functionality of the proposed authentication scheme is analysed and comparison has been made with the existing SSL based Authentication Protocol (SAP) [30] used in the OGSA framework of Globus Middleware.

The biometric matching is not done mostly in the smart card in proposed scheme but rather in the remote server without losing the privacy of the biometric data. The total time taken for the execution of the proposed algorithm is purely based on the crypto-algorithm selected for the process of encryption and decryption.

Table 2 Comparison of Communication Cost

SAP [30]		Proposed Scheme	
Certificate	RSA Signature	RSA Encryption	RSA Signature
2	2	1	1

In table 2 the communication cost of the proposed scheme is compared to the SAP based scheme. The proposed scheme includes only one major Encryption and one Signature operation. RSA based encryption is used since it is considered one of the most secure encryption algorithms.

In our proposed Scheme, Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) based on block cipher is used for symmetric encryption. Since the time taken for AES is very less compared to RSA which is used more frequently, the cost of RSA algorithm is alone considered for analysis. RSA of 1024 bits [31] is used for the Asymmetric Encryption. The AES algorithm used here has a key length of 128 bits and RC4 algorithm of 128 bit key length can be used. The algorithm is executed for an input of a 32 kB biometric finger print image. MD5 scheme has been used for hashing. Any light-weight public-key cryptosystem can be used for the encryption and decryption process.

Table 3 Comparison of Computation Cost and Storage

	SAP [30]	Proposed Scheme
Client	1 ENC _{RSA} , 1 SIG _{RSA} and certificate verification	1 ENC _{RSA}
Server	1 DEC _{RSA} , 1SIG _{RSA} and Authenticating client	1 DEC _{RSA}
Long-Term Storage	Certificates	Biometric Template
Short-Term Storage	Keys, Nonces	Keys, Nonces

From table 3 the computation and storage cost for both the schemes are analysed. The increase in computation and storage cost is mainly due to the maintenance and storage of certificates in the SAP based authentication scheme. The proposed scheme has only storage of biometric template which occupies less space and has less maintenance when compared to certificates.

5.1 Performance Analysis of Proposed Scheme

The platform considered for the simulation of the authentication scheme is GridSim [32]. GridSim is a Java based simulation platform for grid computing. New modules of clients and resources can be integrated into GridSim by rewriting the interfaces. The simulation is done 8 times. The communication and computation cost for execution of the Sap and proposed schemes are analyzed. OpenSSL0.9.7 is used to generate SAP. The existing public-domain fingerprint database FVC2002-DB2 is taken as the input for our fingerprint input [33]. The implementation of the proposed algorithm is based on the following system configuration of Processor Speed – 2.13 GHz, RAM size 512 MB, System Type – 32-bit OS.

Fig. 4 Communication Cost in Bytes

The proposed scheme has a much lesser communication time of an average of 1441 bytes when compared to 6154 bytes of SAP protocols. It is observed from figure 4 that the communication cost of the proposed scheme is approximately 25% of that of the SAP protocol.

Fig. 5 Time taken for Authentication in ms

The proposed Scheme has an average authentication time of 288 ms when compared to that of 1162ms for SAP protocol. The authentication time for the proposed scheme takes 25% of that of SAP protocol. The increase in authentication time for the SAP maybe attributed to the certificate generation and maintenance. From the figure 4 and 5 it is clear that the proposed scheme has lesser communication and authentication cost and hence is also suitable for mobile grid user schemes. It is clear from the data collected that the selection of the encryption algorithm used for encryption influences the time taken for completion of the execution of the process. Lightweight algorithms like

Camellia can be used in place of AES algorithm and Elliptic Curve Cryptography in place of RSA algorithm can also be considered for usage.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

The proposed authentication scheme has provided an enhanced security with an optimal overall time taken for the operation. The authentication scheme can be made more secure by using a triple DES algorithm but it increases the security criteria and also increases the overall time taken for authentication. By increasing the security during the authentication phase itself we can try to minimize any other malicious insider attacks and also reduce external attacks. The biometric data used for authentication can also be used in the consecutive authorization process thereby lessening the database space utilized by reusing the data used in authentication. The AES, RC4 algorithm can be replaced by any other light weight encryption algorithm like camellia. The data's used for authentication can also be used for authorizing the user for a resource access.

7. References

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